

Students' perceptions on three-way pedagogical models hybridization: Contributing to the development of active identities

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Abstract

The goal of the present study was to explore Primary Education students' views on their involvement in a three pedagogical models' hybridization (Health-Based Physical Education, Cooperative Learning and Sport Education) based on their common features, links and frameworks (e.g., the influence of the models in the students' basic psychological needs or motivation), as well as their limitations. A total of 115 year-5 and year-6 students (46.09% girls; aged 10-13 years), enrolled in one school in central Spain, agreed to participate. They all experienced the same "Edu-CrossFit" learning unit (13 lessons, 45 minutes/each). One teacher-researcher, with more than six years of previous experience on pedagogical models, implemented the learning unit. The study followed a qualitative methodology, and four group interviews (one from each participating class) were conducted at the end of the intervention programme. From the students' responses, and to facilitate the understanding and soundness of the data analysed, four main themes emerged: (a) "Am I allowed to behave autonomously?": students' views on how to deal with it'; (b) Students' views on cooperating and relating with partners; (c) Students' feelings on their competence and motivation; and (d) "Not only movers, but informed and habitual movers": building students' active identities. In conclusion, the participating students acknowledged that they had learned to become more autonomous, competent and motivated, to build new relationships and to develop an active identity. A longer-term unit would allow teacher to know students better and to ensure the consolidation of students' learnings. Therefore, despite some limitations, this hybridization can contribute to shaping habitual, motivated, critical and informed movers.

Keywords: Health-Based Physical Education; Cooperative Learning; Sport Education; Models-based practise; Primary Education.

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Introduction

Unfortunately, many physical education (PE) practises focus exclusively on physical achievements, promoting ego goals that thwart students' motivation when they do not achieve set standards (Ryan & Deci, 2017). PE teachers often base their practices on sport contents and skills development, downgrading health-related practices, and diminishing the potential of the subject (Cothran et al., 2006).

In the last decade, research on PE has studied the impact of methods which claim to foster outcomes related to different learning domains (physical, cognitive, social and affective) (Kirk, 2013), enhancing students' holistic and intrinsically personal development, and looking beyond practises focused exclusively on decontextualized sport-skills learning (Siedentop et al., 2020) or healthism (Kirk, 2006). These ideas have been reflected in models-based practise through different works linking the contribution of pedagogical models (PMs) such as Sport Education (SE; Siedentop et al., 2020), Health-Based Physical Education (HBPE; Haerens et al., 2011) or Cooperative Learning (CL; Casey & Goodyear, 2015) to the different learning domains.

Research on these PMs has focused on showing their "hegemony" in specific domains (e.g., HBPE on the physical, Haerens et al., 2011; CL on the social, Casey & Goodyear, 2015), the reason being that the specific features of each PM are better suited for one domain. Then, the question is: how could teachers increase PMs' impact on different outcomes? González-Víllora et al. (2019) reported in their systematic review that the combination or hybridization of two PMs, or some of their features, had expanded the contribution of models-based practise to several domains. For example, hybridizations among SE or CL with Games-Centred Approaches showed improvements in the physical and cognitive domains such as game understanding and tactical-technical skills. The implementation of multi-model programmes supported by Casey and MacPhail (2018) could help achieve a wide range of learnings and improve the quality of the teaching-learning processes. However, some PMs, like HBPE, have never been hybridized. Based on these ideas, the purpose of this study was to take one more step in the study of PMs, exploring Primary Education pupils' perceptions on their involvement in a three-PMs hybridization (SE, CL, HBPE).

Theoretical framework to build the hybridization

SE is aimed at developing enthusiastic, competent and cultivated sportpersons through six features (Siedentop et al., 2020): (a) student's affiliation with a team; (b) sport seasons format for the units; (c) formal competition among teams; (d) students' records keeping; and (e) a final phase with (f) a festive atmosphere. CL has the goal of promoting students' social skills through work in groups emphasising the following elements (Johnson et al., 2013): (a) students' individual responsibility in a part of the group's work; (b) promoting interaction to help each other; (c) positive interdependence in order to achieve common goals; (d) group processing to make decisions; and (e) interpersonal skills to foster communication, management and leadership skills. Finally, HBPE aims to develop healthy lifestyles in students (Haerens et al., 2011) and help them value a physically active lifestyle, in line with Siedentop's (1996) view. Recently, Bowler (2019) and Sammon (2019) outlined how teachers could implement HBPE programmes to help students become habitual, motivated, critical and informed movers, through several features: (a) modifying PA behaviours to foster learning in multiple domains (affective mainly); (b) the use of supportive strategies/resources which promote basic psychological needs (competence, relatedness and autonomy); (c) the prioritization of a 'PA for life' approach; (d) the design of meaningful units/tasks to transfer learnings beyond the school; and (e) the support of interventions by different agents (e.g., family or peer strategies).

The different purposes and features of each PM direct each one towards some specific context or contents. SE focuses primarily on sports contents (Hastie et al., 2011), while HBPE is linked to fitness-related contents (Haerens et al., 2011). Globally, teachers tend to implement more sport-related than health-related contents (Cothran et al., 2006), due to a lack of experience with implementing programmes that use health-related contents beyond fitness tests (Haerens et al., 2011). However, these contents could be essential to promote healthy lifestyles and active identities regarding PA practice (Beltrán-Carrillo et al., 2016) among students who live in a sedentary society with high levels of overweight/obesity and their potential risks on health (Kirk, 2006). They will also help meet the recommendations of PA practise (Harris, 2020): people aged 5-17 should practise at least 60 minutes of moderate-to-vigorous PA daily, including activities to strengthen muscles and bones. Notwithstanding, health-related contents should be taught using adequate approaches like HBPE to overcome the

invitation to increase PA levels without a true pedagogical transference to promote students' learning about how to keep healthy (Haerens et al., 2011).

HBPE's goal is to help students learn to practise PA beyond the view of the body from a biological perspective, concerned, exclusively, with how it works (Johns, 2005). It draws from a holistic lens that integrates three approaches (Peiró-Velert & Devís-Devís, 1995): (a) bio-medical: the body and the effects of exercise on it; (b) psycho-educative: to develop personal lifestyles and well-being; and (c) socio-critical: to promote critical thinking on issues related to physical culture. These ideas are related to the body subjectivities and embodiment (Evans & Rich, 2011; Webb et al., 2008). The individuals construct their subjectivities of the body according to some 'ethics' (Foucault, 1990) conceptualized by the way of living within specific contexts (McCuaig & Quennerstedt, 2018). These subjectivities are re-shaped constantly by its interaction with several factors such as affects, ideals, practises, rules, institutions or objects and other bodies (Coffey, 2015). In PE contexts, this results in setting what prototypes of bodies have to be constructed (Evans & Davies, 2020; Webb et al., 2008), influencing teachers and students' values, attitudes and behaviours to achieve them (Edwards et al., 2016). HBPE focuses on developing healthy lifestyles, not on building prototypes, helping each individual enjoy PA from a particular point of view.

Unfortunately, some limitations have also been acknowledged on each model. Dyson (2002) reported that CL decreased practise time due to organizational and team tasks, while Haerens et al. (2011) pointed out that HBPE tends to be focused on biomedical approaches, and O'Donovan et al. (2010) indicated that SE could promote over-competitiveness, aggressiveness and dominance by skilled boys.

PMs share similar features or pursue common objectives that favour their hybridization: Dyson et al. (2004) suggested that SE and CL provide a situated learning context using meaningful activities, while SE and HBPE pursue the idea that students treasure active identities (Siedentop, 1996). Moreover, the three PMs have been researched linked to one major theoretical framework: the Self-Determination Theory (Ryan & Deci, 2017). Haerens et al. (2011) proposed that the satisfaction of the students' basic psychological needs can increase their motivation and their chances to practise PA beyond the PE lessons, while Chu & Zhang (2018) found that SE foster the satisfaction of these needs (autonomy and competence above all), and Casey & Goodyear (2015) reported that CL is an appropriate framework to enhance the three needs and especially cooperation among students, developing their relatedness.

Grounded on the aforementioned, the goal of the present study was to explore Primary Education students' views on a three-PMs hybridization (HBPE, CL, SE) based on their common features, links and frameworks (e.g., their influence on the basic psychological needs or the promotion of healthy and active identities), as well as their limitations.

Method

Setting, participants and ethics

All year-5 and year-6 students (n= 115; 46.09% girls; 10-13 years) enrolled in one Primary Education school in central Spain (Cuenca), distributed in four natural groups by the school administration (two in each grade) participated. These grades were chosen, because they have been considered suitable to implement PMs hybridizations and health-related contents (González-Víllora et al., 2019; Ward et al., 2017). The school is located in a medium socio-economic, mostly Caucasian neighbourhood. Only seven participating students belonged to other ethnicities (Eastern Europe, Morocco, South-America). All groups and students experienced the same learning unit (13 lessons, 45 minutes/each): an educative version of CrossFit ("Edu-Crossfit"), which included several developmentally appropriate modifications (see in depth in Evangelio et al., in press). Finally, 24 students (six from each class-group) were selected to provide their thoughts on the experience.

A PE-specialist Primary Education teacher (hereinafter referred to as teacher) with more than six years of previous experience on PMs designed and implemented the learning unit. He was not the students' habitual PE teacher. He identified himself as PE teacher to the pupils before the intervention began. The other authors of the manuscript (hereinafter referred to as researchers), with over 20 years on PMs experience, supervised the ongoing process of design and implementation.

Ethical approval and permission by the participating school was granted to conduct the study. The project was also explained to the students, and their parents were informed using the school's online platform. Those who wanted their children to participate handed a written letter of consent prior to enter the study. Privacy and anonymity were guaranteed and pseudonyms were used.

Intervention programme

The hybridization was built around the following considerations to ensure its suitability and its educational value: (1) several experienced and knowledgeable teacher/researchers contributed to avoid Casey and MacPhail's limitation (2018) on the need of previous teacher's knowledge and experience to implement PMs; (2) the theoretical frameworks of the three models (see Table 1), as well as previous hybridizations were reviewed; and (3) the participants' characteristics, as well as the resources and the time available were considered. Regarding the features of PMs, the authors used common frameworks (e.g., the contribution of the three models to the individuals' basic psychological needs promotion) and tried to overcome some of the constraints (e.g., over-competitiveness, which could thwart a positive atmosphere, and work against the principles of CL or HBPE; Johnson et al., 2013; Haerens et al., 2011). Therefore, some changes were made, like changing the SE competition format emphasising students' cooperation and safe and effective exercises instead of winning against others.

[Insert Table 1 here]

On the other hand, students were divided in heterogeneous groups (i.e., gender, skill level) following Johnson et al. (2013) and Siedentop et al.'s (2020) considerations. Moreover, the PMs were implemented following previously published hybridizations (Gonzalez-Villora et al., 2019): (1) autonomy and responsibility were progressively promoted using student's roles in CL structures; (2) the length of the intervention program was in line with previous SE programs conducted in similar students; and (3) the content was adapted to be developmentally appropriate and focused on HBPE principles (see Table 2).

[Insert Table 2 here]

Finally, Hastie and Casey's (2014) fidelity model was followed. A rich description of the lesson plan is included in Table 3 (expanded in Evangelio et al., in press). The programme context has been addressed through (1) the description of the context (i.e., students and school's characteristics or teacher's experience have been outlined in the previous subsection), (2) the different PMs' features included (Table 1) and the phases/stages of each PM. Finally, the validation of the intervention program was conducted assessing the lessons' recordings with an adapted checklist, built using the following references: Hastie et al.'s (2013) SE benchmarks (e.g., groups went to a

designated area and began warming up); Bowler (2019) and Sammon's (2019) HBPE benchmarks (e.g., students set and assess individual/team PA targets); and Casey et al.'s (2015) instrument to evaluate CL critical features (e.g., promotive interaction: students help each other during the tasks). Two independent researchers with training and experience on the three PMs evaluated one third of the recordings and agreed that the intervention was properly conducted.

[Insert Table 3 here]

Data collection

Group interviewing. Four group interviews were conducted at the end of the intervention programme. Each one included six students (St1-St6) selected based on gender, skill level (high, medium, low), roles played (e.g., judge, coach), and involvement (high, medium, low). Each group of six belonged to one of the four classes participating in the study (GI1 and GI2 from 5th grade, and GI3-GI4 from 6th grade). Interviews lasted 30-45 minutes. This qualitative instrument was deemed to be appropriate, because group interviews are desirable when the focus is to obtain data on common held attitudes, beliefs, experiences, interests, and behaviours. Moreover, group interviews favour students' interaction and stimulate discussion from different lenses on one common experience, providing information that would not be available in individual interviews and creating a less threatening environment for students (McQuarrie & McIntyre, 1990). The questions used were developed by the research team (with previous experience in the field), trying not to influence the students to provide desirable answers, and asking objective questions to obtain subjective answers (Bergen & Labonté, 2020). They focused on understanding the students' feelings and thoughts that they had experienced during the intervention programme (e.g., 'What are your thoughts and feelings about having to perform roles? What did they demand from you?'). The interview format was based on open-ended questions to achieve a twofold purpose: to allow the researchers to obtain data about the specific features of the hybridization and to explore the students' responses. Participants were asked about the methodology, the content and the framework (e.g., the progressive transfer of autonomy, the responsibility of performing roles or the cooperation built).

To encourage students' participation, the interviews were conducted in their classrooms, while anonymity was guaranteed using pseudonyms. Similar to previous

works (e.g., Casey & MacPhail, 2018), one member of the research team conducted the interviews. Questions were framed in a colloquial language and a friendly tone so that students could understand them and feel comfortable (e.g., ‘During the lessons you participated in groups; with the same students that you usually practice? How was it?’). Students were encouraged to be honest in their responses because they were going to be kept confidential. All of these considerations helped the research team reduce/avoid the social desirability bias (Bergen & Labonté, 2020). Moreover, the researcher was an active listener who encouraged students to participate and provide detailed accounts to their responses related to the study’s purposes (Smith, 2010).

Data analysis

The information obtained in the data collection process was transcribed verbatim and it was analysed using a multiphase approach, which combined inductive and deductive thematic content analysis and constant comparison (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005), searching for meaningful units of data to support the codes and categories generated (Dale, 2000). These codes, subcategories and categories emerged inductively from the data, identifying similarities and differences from different answers (Miles et al., 2013). They were not predetermined, but the theoretical approaches (SE, HBPE, CL, hybridizations) informed the analysis (deductively) in a general way. It was then that pertinent quotes were selected to illustrate the theory and triangulate information between quotes-theory (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005).

Data were revised in a second round of analysis to improve the reliability of the categories (e.g., ‘students’ positive/negative feelings’, ‘ideas on methodology’ or ‘basic psychological needs’) and subcategories (e.g., respect, responsibility, displeasure with the way some partners performed their roles). All the authors participated in discussing, refining and readjusting the codes and categories. This allowed confirmation and enhanced trustworthiness (Shenton, 2004). The software Atlas.ti 8 was used to analyse the data collected.

Findings and discussion

The goal of this study was to explore Primary Education students’ views on a three-PMs hybridization (HBPE, CL and SE) based on their common features, links and frameworks, as well as their limitations. From the students’ responses, and to facilitate

the understanding and soundness of the data analysed (some methodological considerations arouse positive or negative feelings), the main findings will be presented and discussed around four themes: (a) “Am I allowed to behave autonomously?”: students’ views on how to deal with it; (b) Students’ views on cooperating and relating with partners; (c) Students’ feelings on their competence and motivation; and (d) “Not only movers, but informed and habitual movers”: building students’ active identities.

“Am I allowed to behave autonomously?”: Students’ views on how to deal with it

One of the goals of this hybridization was to increase learners’ autonomy and promote a student-centred approach. Some specific PMs features aimed at supporting students’ autonomy were the use of students’ roles and the development of individual accountability, or the use of some specific resources (role sheets or cards with graphic descriptions of exercises) that helped students remember how to perform an exercise or deal with queries and doubts.

In this hybridization, the teacher who applied the intervention tried to create an environment that would facilitate a student-centred practise where students could assess their physical possibilities, facilitating information and resources to practise the tasks autonomously, listening, responding and motivating them (Bowler, 2019; Sammon, 2019). In this vein, students perceived their autonomy increased because they progressively gained more responsibility (see Table 3):

One thing changed: usually the teacher takes the lead to tell us what to do, and now we can do what we want if we do it well (St5, boy; GI3)

It is not that the teachers have to tell us, we do it ourselves and we try our best (St3, girl; GI3)

Most of the students accepted the transfer of autonomy and indicated that they preferred it to a teacher-centred teaching, similarly to what Casey and Goodyear (2015) on CL and Hastie and Wallhead (2016) on SE reported. However, some preferred some support from the teacher to guide them; a midpoint between students/teacher-centred teaching (Metzler, 2017).

It is better that we do it and not the teacher who hover over us, because, teachers get tired of us not doing the tasks, they are always on top of us saying what to do.

So it seems to me that we have to learn to do the things right by ourselves (St1, girl; GI1)

...a midpoint, the teachers should guide us in the most complicated tasks and we could do the simplest things such as a warm-up (St5, boy; GI3)

The students showed different degrees of responsibility. While most were prepared and motivated to perform their duties and tasks working in groups, as shown by Chu and Zang (2018), other students showed less responsibility to perform their roles or to collaborate in some group tasks at the beginning, as reported by Guijarro et al. (2020) in a SE program. These differences caused displeasure on some students with the way some partners carried out their responsibilities, and therefore some conflicts within some groups (GI2 and GI3) emerged, demotivating a few students in some lessons. Consequently, when they were asked what elements they liked the least or should be modified, some students stated that:

I would change the coach of my group, not because, because he did not listen to us and he did not put the effort to do the tasks. We helped him, but he did not listen and did not tell us what we had to do. (St5, girl; GI2)

...it is difficult to say (there were conflicts), because some group members did not collaborate much; they did not want to practise, and when they did not collaborate there was no fun. (St3, girl; GI3)

In this regard, it is important for the teacher to understand when each student was ready to perform each specific task autonomously. So, a limitation of this proposal was the teacher's lack of knowledge about the students' characteristics. A longer-term unit, even though its length (13 lessons of 45 minutes) was in line with previous hybridizations (González-Víllora et al., 2019) and SE considerations (Siedentop et al., 2020), would have allowed the teacher to conduct more guided lessons, or hand over autonomy more gradually, knowing more accurately when the students were ready to take on certain responsibilities. Prior to this program, students had not participated in pedagogical approaches that required them to play a leading role, and not everyone was prepared to perform it. However, scaffolding the autonomy/responsibilities transference (Farias et al., 2018; Gillies & Haynes, 2011) and some CL features could help students get ready and ensure their effective integration, as it is shown in the following section.

Students' views on cooperating and relating with partners

Casey et al. (2015) claim that promoting the CL element of students' individual accountability previous to transfer full autonomy, through supportive strategies such as working in groups or roles, could be effective to help students feel confident and successful in the different tasks and to develop cooperation. In the present study, students expressed that groups and roles were positive not only to achieve these goals, but also to learn because they integrated the information better from peers (Casey et al., 2015).

What I liked the most was that it was in a group, because once you are in a group you are encouraged to do well. (St6, girl; GI1)

I understand things better with my classmates, instead of having a teacher explaining them to me. (St2, boy; GI3)

everyone needs to contribute to the group (roles), if you do nothing, it is like if you are not part of the team. (St4, girl; GI3)

Students identified another key element of CL: equal opportunities for all students (Slavin & Cooper, 1999) to participate and perform their duties. Casey et al. (2015), in CL, or Guijarro et al. (2020), in SE, found that some students, or roles, increased their responsibility based on their implication in the lessons or on their personal characteristics. The present hybridization was designed so that all roles had similar tasks to perform to promote all students' involvement and learning.

...not to be selfish and do everything yourself; let others do something. (St2, girl; GI1)

... the roles, as the sessions went on, we looked at them differently, because they were good and we liked that everyone was important in our team. (St2, boy; GI2)

To way to create the working groups to make them heterogeneous and not allowing close friends in the same group, help students to develop new bonds, and it worked, since they met new partners and built friendships (Dyson et al., 2020).

Work with new classmates. Before, when we played in pairs or groups, we always get together with the same people. So, we have socialized with others. (St1, girl; GI1)

The way groups were arranged was not always positive because, at time, the less responsible pupils did not want to cooperate, and achieve the group's objectives was harder (Goodyear et al., 2014). The students need time to understand how important it was to cooperate with other teammates. Research tells us that it is a mistake to begin an intervention programme that involves cooperation without taking this idea into consideration (Casey et al., 2015; Gillies & Haynes, 2011). Therefore, this intervention started with the use of CL techniques and games focused on building students' confidence on each other (Fernández-Río, 2016). They participated in tasks to know each other better and to build confidence on each other. After, CL techniques like collective score were used to build cooperation in the class-group (each individual added to the group), and learning teams where students worked in trios supervised by the coach or the judge to practice the exercises properly and provide feedback. Only then, when students' cooperation and group processing skills (Johnson et al., 2013) were stronger, they participated in more complex CL techniques such as 'Think, share, perform' (i.e., each student thinks individually a solution to solve the problem and achieve the goal and shares it with the rest of the group to debate on the best one and try it) or 'Jigsaw' (i.e., students from different groups meet to solve problems or provide help to improve their work).

After the first three lessons, I gained confidence with my teammates. We felt closer (St2, boy; GI2)

...Confidence is important. If you do not have it or if you do not get along with a person, you will not be able to work well. (St2, boy; GI3)

Another essential characteristic was the modified SE competition format. Students were not pushed to outperform others, only to outperform themselves (i.e., setting goals and self-evaluate them, not beating other groups), to help peers, to focus on their learning (e.g., how to perform the exercise in a safe way from a HBPE perspective; Peiró-Velert & Devís-Devís, 1995) and become involved (Bowler, 2019; Casey & Goodyear, 2015). Consequently, this hybridization overcame one potential SE constraint: over-competitiveness (O'Donovan et al., 2010).

...[I prefer] doing the exercises well, because if you do nothing or you do them wrong, you are fooling yourself. (St2, girl; GI1)

...some partners challenged each other, but it was ok because the goal was to outperform oneself and that extra effort was good. (St2, boy; GI2)

[I participated] just for sport and fun. (St3, girl; GI3)

Even when students were asked which workouts they liked the most, comparing those in the ‘final phase’ (when there was a winner) or those during the ‘modified formal competition’, all students from GI3 agreed that they preferred doing them ‘during the ‘modified formal competition’.

Students’ feelings on their competence and motivation

Cooperation among students helped them identify and understand the importance of social values and interpersonal skills (Johnson et al., 2013) such as respect (Dyson, 2002; Harvey et al., 2014) or trust (Bowler, 2019; Hastie & Wallhead, 2016) to work in groups.

Respect, because not everyone performs at the same pace; no one should complain... I had partners that I have never worked with before. We built confidence. (St3, girl; GI4)

Students discovered their partners’ capabilities and limitations, as well as their own competence (Biddle et al., 2011; Casey & Goodyear, 2015; Hastie & Wallhead, 2016). It helped develop ‘motivated movers’, linked to HBPE (Bowler, 2019; Sammon, 2019). Group interactions, developed through SE affiliation and the practise of exercises together, also favoured positive interdependence within groups (CL feature; Johnson et al., 2013) and the appreciation of their partners’ different bodies or physical characteristics, reducing some risks linked to body image stereotypes (Evans & Rich, 2011; Webb et al., 2008).

I discovered that my partners had skills that I did not know they had, and that when they did not achieve the goal, they tried hard. This makes the group stronger. (St2, boy; GI2)

...if a person is fatter, you do not have to tease him, you have to respect him. (St5, boy; GI4)

Students’ increased their motivation during the lessons. They probably felt that their partners knew them and encouraged them to practise (Bowler, 2019). Their relatedness and competence seemed to increase (Ryan & Deci, 2017) and, consequently, they became engaged in the PE lessons and physical activity (PA) practise, in relation to HBPE (Haerens et al., 2011). According to Biddle et al. (2011) and Harris (2000), this

feeling of competence could more likely carry into future intentions to be physically active and transfer beyond the school.

Furthermore, the use of health-related contents linked to endurance and strength was well regarded, compared with the contents they were used to practising. Students became motivated probably because they discovered that they were capable of performing tasks/exercises that they did not know that they could do. Since these were challenging (Cale, 2020), students enjoyed the efforts required to perform them. The adaptability of the content was a supportive factor to create an educative version of 'Edu-Crossfit' adapting all the exercises (Evangelio et al., in press).

Before, In PE we did more relaxed activities. (St5, girl; GI4)

I liked "Edu-Crossfit". At first, I wanted to practise it. Then, I lost interest, but when I got used to the exercises, I did not find it so hard and I ended liking it. (St5, boy; GI3)

I enjoyed the exercises with the balls because they were similar to those made by professionals. (St3, boy; GI1)

... it is like the "push-ups". Imagine that you want to do them at home. Before, I did not know, but now I do. (St2, boy; GI3)

Students showed a preference for this content because it was new compared to the ones they had experienced before. Current research has reported that novelty is a variable that can promote students' intrinsic motivation (González-Cutre & Sicilia, 2019).

I prefer this sport because we have learned another sport, not always the same ones (St2, girl; GI1)

I thought we were going to perform circuits with cones.... When I heard "Edu-Crossfit", I was intrigued. When I knew, it was fun, a good experience... the warm-ups and the exercises were very different. (St2, boy; GI2)

Notwithstanding, the student-centered framework must acknowledge the teacher's ability to enhance, strengthen and foster students' learning (Hattie, 2009). In the present hybridization, students and teachers spent enough time during the season to learn and teach according to their needs (Casey & MacPhail, 2018; Goodyear & Dudley, 2015), and the students perceived their autonomy (Ryan & Deci, 2017) along with the teacher's support.

I think it was better for us to conduct almost everything, because we begin to be responsible for what we do (St3, girl; GI3)

Not only movers, but informed and habitual movers: Building students' active identities

The teacher during the implementation programme tried to improve the students' ability to learn autonomously, using strategies such as reciprocal teaching, feedback or goal setting (Goodyear & Dudley, 2015). To achieve consolidated health-related learnings linked to the content, the teacher assumed greater responsibility in the "preseason" to introduce and supervise students' safe and effective practise of health-related exercises. Later, during the 'student-guided lessons', the teacher tried to promote students' learnings on healthy considerations and their implications, while he supervised the exercises (Bowler, 2019; Haerens et al., 2011). In this phase, the teacher scaffolded the transference of responsibility to coaches and judges, who had to supervise theirs and their peers' practise (Farias et al., 2018). Therefore, the teacher's role was dependent on the students' requirements (Hattie, 2009) and the exercises/tasks' presentation of the health-related content (Metzler, 2017). For this reason, his experience and knowledge on the PMs hybridized was a key element (Casey & MacPhail, 2018), as well as on the content (Haerens et al., 2011).

Although we had to do the tasks and exercises autonomously, we shared doubts with the group...Sometimes also with the teacher, [in particular] technical issues (St5, girl; GI2)

... since I was the coach and there was a boy who did not perform the "walking lunges" well, I showed him. But he continued to do them wrong... I showed him again, and he finally did. (St1, girl; GI2)

Some resources supported the students' autonomous learning and how to perform their responsibilities and the exercises (e.g., role sheets or exercise cards). Thus supported the students' autonomy (Bowler, 2019) and the tenets of the psycho-educational theoretical perspective linked to HBPE (Peiró-Velert & Devís-Devis, 1995).

One resource had a greater impact on students: the "judges sheets", which served to identify in which elements students needed to work daily, set goals and self-evaluate (Goodyear & Dudley, 2015). This process helped students become 'informed movers' (Bowler, 2019) and improved their knowledge of their own physical

capabilities (Haerens et al., 2011), promoting effective learning. This sheets helped students to set goals to meet, as reported by López-Pastor et al. (2013) in their review on alternative assessment, that included the influence of self-assessment in the students' learning. For this reason, students needed some time (lessons) to learn how to set the right goals, because they had to learn what, how and how much (Goodyear & Dudley, 2015). This resource contributed to avoid conflicts produced by some students' lack of responsibility or involvement in the lessons, becoming a positive mechanism for conflict resolution (Siedentop et al., 2020). However, the teacher perceived a limitation here, because he had to provide more information on how to set goals, how to solve conflicts or take advantage of the sheets' pedagogical potential.

We met most of the goals, but, sometimes, we set very difficult or very easy goals, we did not know how to reach the middle point. (St5, boy; GI4)

Yes, we met the goals: did not argue in the group, promoted friendship and tried our best to do things right. (St5, girl; GI2)

We set goals to improve our behaviour. We were always arguing, because some did nothing, so we set them, although they were difficult to meet. (St7, girl; GI3)

Establishing a daily routine to perform in the lessons was another supportive resource. The routine helped the students guide the lessons autonomously, because they knew what to do, and why they were doing things. It also allowed the students to avoid confusion about what to perform during the lessons (as mentioned by Siedentop et al., 2020), and to focus on learning about their practise.

If you warm up, you have less chances of being injured. At the end, you can stretch, so your muscles do not hurt. (St2, boy; GI3)

If you do not have a routine [to exercise], there will be no order... (St2, girl; GI1)

Therefore, the use of the aforementioned resources to support the students' autonomous learning resulted in an increase of their knowledge on PA practise and its health considerations (e.g., the importance of warm-ups or safe and effective exercising), which are linked to the tenets of the bio-medical and psycho-educational approaches related to HBPE (Peiró-Velert & Devís-Devís, 1995) and consequently to the goal of developing 'informed movers' (Bowler, 2019; Sammon, 2019). The teacher tried to promote the transference of these learning to real life situations (e.g., how to lift

heavy loads lifting the students' school bags) to help students use them beyond the PE lessons (Biddle et al., 2011; Haerens et al., 2011; Harris, 2000).

...for example, helping our parents with the housework, we knew how to lift things without getting hurt. (St2, boy; GI2)

... I carried my backpack upstairs to the dining room; before, I hurt my back many times because I did not know how to hold it well, and after learning the squats I do not hurt myself anymore. (St3, boy; GI2)

I think that what we have learnt here, we can do it out with our friends, and everyone would be fit. (St4, girl; GI3)

The teacher conducted discussions about the contents' benefits (related to the strength and endurance workout) identifying how to overcome barriers to practise it beyond the lessons, following the socio-critical approach of HBPE (Kirk, 2006; Peiró-Velert & Devís-Devís, 1995), the idea of educating 'critical movers' to help students also become 'habitual movers' (Bowler, 2019), and 'valuing a physically active life' (Siedentop, 1996).

...to move, at least every day try to do some sport or exercise. Some days, if we did not have extracurricular activities or PE, we sat all day, even when we got home to do our homework, sat again.... (St2, boy; GI2)

Moreover, it helped students perceive their bodies and generated discussions about the relevance of engaging in regular exercise, risk prevention, healthy lifestyles and physical training (Webb et al., 2008). The students valued being healthy beyond their bodies (Evans & Davies, 2020), and increased their efforts in the lessons (Edwards et al., 2016). This idea was shaped by their interactions with objects and partners with different bodies and fitness (Coffey, 2015).

If we exercise daily, even at home, we will be healthier and fit. (St3, girl; GI3)

It is important to exercise and keep fit because now nothing happens, but when we get older [the lack of exercise] can cause us trouble [e.g., heart diseases]...And we have to keep exercising when we grow up. (St4, girl; GI3)

The results highlighted that the hybridization contributed to achieving Siedentop et al.'s (2020) goal of educating literate, competent and enthusiastic students and to help students to achieve significant learnings and develop active identities (Bowler, 2019; Casey et al., 2015).

Conclusions

To our knowledge, there is no prior evidence of the hybridization of HBPE or three different PMs (González-Víllora et al., 2019). Results from the present study highlight the potentialities of hybridizing three models (SE, CL and HBPE) when teaching a novel health-related content, Edu-Crossfit. The students acknowledged that they had learnt to become more autonomous and build new relationships, motivated by a student-centred practise, where they learnt with their peers. However, findings also revealed that before handing over autonomy, teachers need to assess to what extent students can behave with responsibility and cooperation, and provide activities accordingly to help this transfer. The lack of teacher's knowledge on the students prior to the intervention caused the emergence of some conflicts due to the differences on students' ability to carry out the activities with responsibility that hindered the expected progress of the intervention. Students' participation was also characterized by their feelings of competence and motivation supported and encouraged by their group partners during the class work, their ability to perform challenging tasks, and a preference to engage in the Edu-Crossfit content. These considerations, along with the use of supportive pedagogical resources and students' participation in classroom debates on critical issues related to HBPE contents, facilitated the acquisition of knowledge on how to practice PA in a healthy way, and the transfer of some learning and experiences to students' life outside school.

Although the involvement in the hybridization may contribute to the development of students' active identities regarding PA, it was not an aim of the present study to check whether students increased their PA practise in their leisure time or whether it lasted over time, beyond the students' intentions shown during the program and the interviews. Future research should explore how this type of interventions may help to the transfer of PE learning to extracurricular activities and consequently to the consolidation of students' active identities or, on the contrary, what is learnt and experienced in PE do not permeate the bounds of the school grounds. Nevertheless, the results showed that the present hybridization can contribute to shaping habitual, motivated, critical, and informed movers. Different possibilities are opened with this hybridization on the models-based practice, thus future and similar practices need to be applied in other contexts to get more insight on students' experiences and compare their results, or new hybridizations including other PMs should also be explored.

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Table 1*Features of the hybridized models.*

Sport Education	Health-Based Physical Ed.	Cooperative learning
Season format: lesson plan was divided in pre-season, season and culminating event	Teacher promoted a motivating learning climate with positive feedback, encouragement and energy for PA practise	Promotive interaction: students participated face-to-face interactions to promote each others' success
Affiliation: students were divided into permanent groups, except in lessons 1-2 when they worked with other groups to build cohesiveness	Collaboration among students improved their social skills, knowing partners better and building friendships (relatedness)	Group processing: decisions were agreed by all group members, including some roles decisions which affected the group
Formal competition: it was modified to meet the other models; groups had to try to meet their goals for each lesson, except in the final one	Teacher discussed about the relevance of PA practise for health and elaborated resources to support learning of health concepts/values. Students practised autonomously (psycho-educative approach)	Interpersonal skills: students worked on social skills to debate on group decisions, to understand that each partner had personal capabilities/limitations and to solve conflicts.
Culminating event: in the last session groups paraded with music before the final games and concluded with an awards ceremony	Students learned how to perform PA safe and effectively, health-based PA concepts (bio-medical approach); error was used as a resource to learn (not a limitation)	Positive interdependence: students depended on their group-partners to achieve common goals; each one tried their best to help reach the group's goals on each lesson
Festivity: the whole unit was involved in a festive and positive atmosphere to increase students' motivation	Students discussed about the benefits/risks to practise PA during the programme and after (socio-critical approach)	Individual responsibility: each student had individual duties with the roles and participated actively to achieve the group targets on each lesson.
Record keeping: students tried to improve their own marks, and they motivated other teams to improve theirs	Teacher handed autonomy to the students progressively; materials, work routines, roles and self-evaluation were strategies used	

Table 2

Brief explanation of the “Edu-CrossFit” characteristics.

“Edu-CrossFit” was adapted to meet the recommendations of PA practice for people aged 5-17 and based on functional movements adaptable to fit each practitioner needs or fitness.

All the exercises were practiced before the workouts. Teacher supervised and highlighted the safe and effective practice.

Teacher introduced the exercises progressively based on their difficulty, transferring autonomy gradually to students.

All workouts were completed in groups to achieve common goals. Students could complete their exercises in cooperation with their peers or individually.

Competition was avoided, and students from different groups could help each other, ensuring that students focused on performing the exercises correctly, not fast.

“Edu-CrossFit” was used to transfer learning to their life outside the school such as carrying their schoolbags.

Table 3*Brief description of the lesson plan (see in depth in Evangelio et al., in press).*

Sport Education	Cooperative learning	Health-Based PE	Lesson	Contents developed
Preseason.	Phase 1	Teacher guided lessons	1	Group formation; group cohesion and self-awareness tasks; introduction of the didactic resources (e.g. roles sheets or 'coach' exercises).
			2	
		Phase 2	Teacher handed over autonomy to the students	3
	4			
	5			
	Modified formal competition	Phase 3	Students guided lessons	6
7				
8				
9				
10				
Final phase and festivity	Phase 3	Students guided lessons	11	Teacher explained the structure: groups' parade, warm-up, final training/competition, cool-down and awards ceremony; festive atmosphere; intergroup cooperation and encouragement
			12	
			13	